

STUDIES ON THE DESULPHURISATION OF HIGH SULPHUR INDIAN COALS. PART IV

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Effect of different catalysts, viz., sodium silicate, silica, hydrated alumina, bauxite and magnesium chloride, on desulphurisation of coal during carbonisation in presence of different gases (steam, coal gas, hydrogen and ammonia) has been studied.

In previous communications¹⁻³, the authors investigated the effects of different atmospheres during carbonisation of a sample of coal from Baragolai colliery, Assam and it was found that nascent hydrogen facilitated increased desulphurisation. The present investigation deals with the effects of different catalysts (foreign substances) on the desulphurisation during carbonisation in presence of different gases. For this, a number of catalysts which served the purpose in our earlier communications¹⁻³ have been chosen and their actions have been studied in presence of steam, coal gas, hydrogen and ammonia respectively. The object here is to ascertain the effect of combined actions of the gas and the catalyst, and how far the catalysts help in the decomposition of the gases and consequent desulphurisation of the coal sample.

Literature indicates that the effects of different gases and vapours in presence of different catalysts have not been extensively studied although some of the investigators have studied the effects of different gases only during carbonisation. Ghose and Brewer⁴ have studied the effect of ammonia gas in presence of catalysts like FeO and Al₂O₃ in different proportions. They have stated that Al₂O₃ helped much in the decomposition of ammonia at high temperature and consequent desulphurisation. Lissner⁵ has utilised a mixture of MgCl₂ and lime as the catalyst while carbonising a sample of coal in presence of hydrogen containing gas.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used is the same as that used in our previous experiments¹⁻³.

The catalysts used were powdered to the same mesh as the coal sample, thoroughly mixed with the latter, moistened with a little water, again thoroughly mixed and dried at $105^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ and the mass was used as a test sample. The coal sample was ground to pass through a 60 mesh B. S. sieve and retained on a 80 mesh before mixing with the catalysts. Powell⁶ states that the original state of subdivision of the coal does not affect the desulphurisation process. Sodium silicate was used in the jelly form. As in our previous investigations, the requisite amount of the sodium silicate jelly

was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot water, the coal sample thoroughly mixed with it and the whole dried at $105^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for 1.5 to 2 hours and used as test samples. Superheated steam was not employed this time as it gave none too encouraging results.

The specifications and analyses, as the case may be, of the catalysts used are the same as that reported earlier ¹⁻³.

TABLE I

Effect of sodium silicate (jelly) in presence of steam.

Coal used in each experiment = 16 g. Reaction temp. = 850° .

Expt. No.	Na ₂ SiO ₃ (jelly) added.	Vol. of steam passed at N. T. P.	Time of carbonisation.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.	Nature of coke.
1	2%	7.5 litres	2 hrs.	6.81 g.	2.50%	Caking
2	"	42.1	3	6.80	2.03	"
3	"	62.2	4	6.76	1.46	Semi-caking
4	"	185.7	5	6.52	1.50	"
5	"	286.2	6	6.01	1.41	Non-caking
6	3	14.9	2	6.80	2.94	Caking
7	"	22.4	4	6.79	2.70	"
8	"	37.3	5	6.75	2.61	"
9	"	51.6	6	6.52	2.55	"
10	4	8.6	2	6.82	2.12	"
11	"	14.3	3	6.79	2.35	"
12	"	16.9	5	6.79	2.10	"
13	"	17.4	6	6.78	1.85	"

TABLE II

Effect of silica in presence of steam.

Coal used = 16 g. Reaction temp. = 850° .

Expt. No.	SiO ₂ added.	Steam passed at N. T. P.	Time of carbonisation.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.	Nature of coke.
1	4%	37.3 litres	5.0 hrs.	6.76 g.	1.86%	Caking
2	"	42.1	5.5	6.73	1.81	"
3	"	58.5	6.0	6.71	1.80	Semi-caking
4	5	5.0	3.0	6.85	1.95	Caking
5	"	31.7	4.0	6.77	1.77	"
6	"	43.6	5.0	6.72	1.65	"
7	"	52.5	6.0	6.69	1.20	"
8	6	43.6	5.0	6.73	1.62	"
9	"	45.1	5.5	6.71	1.58	"
10	"	50.6	6.0	6.70	1.52	"

TABLE III

Effect of hydrated alumina in presence of steam.

Coal used = 16 g. Reaction temp. = 850° . Time of carbonisation = 6 hrs.

Expt. No.	Hydrated alumina added.	Steam passed at N. T. P.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.	Nature of coke.
1	0.5%	50.9 litres	6.72 g.	1.83%	Caking
2	1.0	50.86	6.74	2.13	"
3	1.5	51.12	6.70	1.99	"
4	2.0	50.75	6.73	2.06	"
5	2.5	51.23	6.71	2.15	"
6	3.0	51.30	6.70	1.92	"

TABLE IV

Effect of bauxite in presence of steam.

Coal used = 16 g. Reaction temp. = 850°. Time = 6 hrs.

Expt. No.	Bauxite added.	Steam passed at N. T. P.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.	Nature of coke.
1	1%	51.2 litres	6.69 g.	2.21%	Caking
2	2	50.6	6.71	2.06	"
3	3	52.9	6.70	2.16	"
4	4	53.5	6.70	1.95	"
5	5	52.8	6.70	2.19	"

TABLE V

Effect of coal gas in presence of different catalysts.

Coal used in each case = 16 g.

Expt. No.	Catalyst used.	Amount of catalyst.	Coal gas passed in lit./hr.	Reaction temp.	Time of carbonisation.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.
1	SiO ₂	4%	2.0	850°	6 hrs.	8.32 g.	2.01%
2	"	"	3.0	"	"	8.00	1.98
3	"	"	3.5	"	"	8.15	1.97
4	"	5%	2.0	500°	"	8.12	2.06
5	"	"	2.0	700°	"	8.01	1.98
6	"	"	2.5	750°	"	7.95	1.95
7	"	"	2.0	800°	"	7.91	1.81
8	"	"	2.0	850°	"	7.98	1.51
9	"	6%	2.0	"	5	7.92	2.12
10	"	"	2.0	"	6	8.10	2.07
11	"	"	3.5	"	6	7.93	2.02
12	Na ₂ SiO ₃	2%	2.5	"	4	8.52	2.50
13	"	"	2.0	"	6	8.35	2.10
14	"	1.5	2.0	"	6	8.20	2.31
15	"	2.5	2.5	"	4	7.98	2.62
16	"	"	2.5	"	6	8.00	2.40
17	CaO	0.5	2.0	"	"	8.12	2.12
18	"	1.0	2.0	"	"	8.08	2.31
19	"	1.5	2.0	"	"	8.11	2.35
20	"	2.0	2.0	"	"	7.98	2.23
21	"	2.5	2.0	"	"	8.15	2.08
22	MgCl ₂ :CaO	1:1	2.0	500°	"	8.08	1.31
23	"	1:1	"	850°	"	7.94	2.04
24	"	1:2	"	500°	"	8.25	2.46
25	"	1:2	"	850°	"	8.00	2.15
26	"	1:3	"	500°	"	8.08	2.35
27	"	1:3	"	850°	"	8.11	2.82
28	"	2:1	"	500°	"	8.25	2.07
29	"	2:1	"	850°	"	8.12	2.21
30	"	2:2	"	500°	"	8.65	2.47
31	"	2:2	"	850°	"	8.45	2.62
32	"	2:3	"	500°	"	8.09	2.04
33	"	2:3	"	850°	"	8.00	1.81
34	"	3:1	"	500°	"	8.20	1.89
35	"	3:1	"	850°	"	8.00	1.94
36	"	3:2	"	500°	"	8.70	1.76
37	"	3:2	"	850°	"	8.27	2.13
38	"	3:3	"	500°	"	8.18	1.97
39	"	3:3	"	850°	"	7.90	2.11
40	MgCl ₂	1.0%	"	"	"	8.35	1.98
41	"	1.5	"	"	"	8.26	2.02
42	"	2.0	"	"	"	8.27	2.08
43	"	2.5	"	"	"	8.23	2.09
44	"	3.0	"	"	"	8.21	2.11
45	Hydrated alumina	0.5%	"	"	"	8.07	1.41
46	"	1%	"	"	"	8.30	1.40
47	"	1.5	"	"	"	8.11	1.49
48	"	2.0	"	"	"	8.15	1.62
49	"	2.5	"	"	"	8.21	1.73
50	"	3.0	"	"	"	8.23	1.95

TABLE VI

Effect of hydrogen in presence of different catalysts.

Coal used in each case = 16 g. Time of carbonisation = 4 hours.

Reaction temp. = 800°.

Expt. No.	Catalyst added.	Amount of catalyst added.	H ₂ gas passed at N. T. P. (lit.)	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.
1	SiO ₂	2%	7.23	8.21 g.	2.01%
2	"	3	7.28	8.19	1.79
3	"	4	7.16	8.18	1.71
4	"	5	7.22	8.15	1.68
5	"	6	7.18	8.18	1.70
6	"	7	7.20	8.18	1.69
7	Na ₂ SiO ₃ (jelly)	1	7.27	8.22	1.81
8	"	2	7.26	8.20	1.26
9	"	3	7.28	8.21	1.41
10	"	4	7.23	8.19	1.52
11	"	5	7.21	8.20	1.58
12	NaCl	10	7.11	8.11	2.15
13	"	20	7.18	8.05	2.04
14	"	30	7.23	7.99	1.51
15	"	40	7.21	8.01	1.13
16	"	50	7.25	8.00	1.00

TABLE VII

Effect of ammonia gas in presence of different catalysts.

Time of carbonisation = 4 hrs. Reaction temp. = 800°.

Expt. No.	Catalyst added.	Amount of catalyst.	Ammonia consumed.	Coke obtd.	Sulphur in coke.
1	SiO ₂	2%	2.25 g.	8.38 g.	1.68%
2	"	3	2.21	8.30	1.41
3	"	4	2.29	8.27	1.23
4	"	5	2.30	8.23	1.07
5	"	6	2.19	8.24	1.11
6	"	7	2.15	8.26	1.18
7	Na ₂ SiO ₃	1	2.21	8.15	1.50
8	"	2	2.39	8.03	1.04
9	"	3	2.32	8.06	1.18
10	"	4	2.33	8.05	1.16
11	"	5	2.31	8.06	1.18
12	NaCl	10	2.10	8.41	1.81
13	"	20	2.11	8.35	1.77
14	"	30	2.10	8.31	1.71
15	"	40	2.11	8.29	1.64
16	"	50	2.15	8.28	1.60
17	Bauxite	1	2.21	8.31	1.69
18	"	2	2.47	8.26	1.30
19	"	3	2.61	8.25	1.23
20	"	4	2.85	8.20	1.18
21	"	5	3.01	8.15	1.00

Analysis of bauxite used furnished the following data: Insoluble = 1.44%; Fe₂O₃ = 2.7%; TiO₂ = 8.50%; Al₂O₃ = 58.48% (Bauxite is of Indian origin).

TABLE VIII

Distribution of sulphur in the products of carbonisation.

Sulphur in coal = 0.7312 g.

Table No.	Expt. No.	In coke.	In tar & liquor.	H ₂ S.	Sulphur in gases as				In residual gas.
					Mercaptan	Thiophene.	CS ₂ .	COS.	
I	3	0.090 g.	0.120 g.	0.502 g.	0.005 g.	0.002 g.	0.002 g.	Trace	Trace
I	5	0.085	0.124	0.509	0.005	0.002	0.002	"	0.002 g.
I	9	0.166	0.109	0.441	0.005	0.003	Trace	0.002	0.002
I	12	0.143	0.114	0.461	0.004	0.003	0.002	Trace	Trace
I	13	0.125	0.120	0.475	0.004	0.003	Trace	"	"
II	3	0.121	0.125	0.469	0.006	0.003	0.003	"	"
II	7	0.081	0.129	0.510	0.005	0.003	0.002	"	"
II	10	0.102	0.126	0.488	0.005	0.003	0.002	0.002	"
III	1	0.123	0.118	0.476	0.005	0.003	0.002	Trace	"
IV	4	0.131	0.113	0.473	0.006	0.004	0.002	"	"
V	3	0.161	0.096	0.453	0.011	0.006	0.002	"	"
V	8	0.121	0.067	0.516	0.016	0.006	0.003	"	"
V	22	0.106	0.101	0.406	0.009	0.006	0.002	"	"
V	33	0.145	0.079	0.469	0.010	0.005	0.002	"	"
V	36	0.155	0.098	0.464	0.006	0.005	0.001	Nil	"
V	40	0.165	0.104	0.443	0.008	0.007	0.002	Trace	"
V	45	0.114	0.098	0.493	0.011	0.008	0.002	"	0.002
VI	4	0.137	0.101	0.480	0.004	0.003	0.001	"	Trace
VI	8	0.103	0.114	0.500	0.007	0.004	0.002	"	"
VI	16	0.080	0.122	0.508	0.009	0.007	0.002	"	0.002
VII	4	0.088	0.121	0.502	0.008	0.004	0.001	"	0.002
VII	5	0.092	0.119	0.500	0.009	0.005	0.003	0.002	Trace
VII	8	0.084	0.121	0.504	0.009	0.007	0.003	0.001	"
VII	10	0.093	0.112	0.503	0.009	0.007	0.003	0.002	"
VII	16	0.133	0.093	0.487	0.007	0.006	0.002	Trace	"
VII	21	0.081	0.118	0.511	0.009	0.006	0.003	"	"

DISCUSSION

Table I shows the effect of sodium silicate in presence of steam. When 2% sodium silicate was used, the sulphur in coke came down to 1.41% ; of course, the volume of steam passed in such case was great and probably that was the reason why the coke was non-caking in nature. With increase in the percentage of sodium silicate the rate of desulphurisation decreased, but the coke assumed a caking nature.

When 5% silica (on the wt. of coal) was used in an atmosphere of steam, the maximum desulphurisation was attained and the sulphur in coke came down to 2% (vide Table II). The coke in almost all the cases are caking in nature. In these cases also the maximum amount of sulphur in coal evolved as H₂S.

Tables III and IV show the effects of hydrated alumina and bauxite respectively in presence of steam. In case of alumina the maximum desulphurisation was obtained when 0.5% of the catalyst was used and with bauxite it was 4%. In the former case the sulphur in coke was 1.83% and in the latter it was 1.95%. The cokes in all the cases were caking ones.

Table V indicates the effect of coal gas in presence of different catalysts, viz., SiO_2 , Na_2SiO_3 , $\text{MgCl}_2 + \text{CaO}$, CaO , MgCl_2 , and hydrated alumina. These results, when compared with those obtained when only coal gas is used³, show that the above catalysts, with the possible exception of hydrated alumina, hardly show any better effect in presence of coal gas than when coal gas is used alone. The maximum desulphurisation obtained in presence of coal gas alone was when the sulphur in coke came down to 1.41%. In the present case, with hydrated alumina, the best result was obtained when using 1% of the substance the sulphur in coke came down to 1.40%. Using a mixture of MgCl_2 and CaO in the ratio of 1:1 the sulphur in coke came down to 1.31% when carbonisation was carried out at 500°. With a mixture of MgCl_2 and CaO it was found that desulphurisation was better during low temperature than during high temperature carbonisation.

Table VI indicates the effect of hydrogen gas in presence of different inorganic materials. With the different materials used, the maximum desulphurisations obtained were as recorded below :

With 5% SiO_2 the sulphur in coke came down to 1.68% ; with 2% Na_2SiO_3 it was 1.26% and with 50% NaCl it was 1%. The percentage of NaCl was not increased beyond 50% because that would lead to a greater corrosion of inner lining of the furnace in actual operations. The chance of corrosion is minimised in such cases as the gas (H_2 in this case) tends to wipe off the volatile chlorides from the furnace during its passage. The volume of hydrogen gas passed was approximately the same in all the cases.

Table VII shows the effects of ammonia gas in presence of different catalysts, viz., SiO_2 , Na_2SiO_3 , NaCl and bauxite of Indian origin. The maximum desulphurisations obtained in these cases are as follows: With 5% SiO_2 , the sulphur in coke came down to 1.07% ; with 2% Na_2SiO_3 it was 1.04%, with 50% NaCl it was 1.60% and with 5% bauxite it was 1%. Tables VI and VII also indicate that with ammonia and hydrogen gas and in presence of catalysts, the general rate of desulphurisation increases to a marked extent. The volume of ammonia gas passed was approximately the same in all the cases.

Table VIII shows the general distribution of sulphur in the products of carbonisation and shows that maximum amount of gas is evolved as H_2S ,

from which sulphur can be recovered by any of the commercially feasible methods.

R E F E R E N C E S

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